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Research Data Management Plan — Clinical Studies

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This RDMP was created on	by [Name, Department]:
The RDMP was updated on	by [Name, Department]:
The RDMP was updated on	by [Name, Department]:
The RDMP was updated on	by [Name, Department]:
The RDMP was last updated on	by [Name, Department]:

No.	Question	Answer
1	General information on research proposal	
1.1	What is the full title of the study? (baseline study or further study as part of the baseline study)	The title of the study:
1.2	What is the primary research question?	The primary research question is:
1.3	Which institution or individual is responsible for project management and coordination?	Personal name
		Organizational name
		Project manager / sponsor (primary)
		Name of the affiliation:
		Address of the affiliation:
		Webpage of the affiliation:
1.4	Which project partners are there (institutions, persons)?	ROR ID of the affiliation:
		Personal name
		Organizational name
		Personal name (if applicable)
		Type of role of partner:

Name of the affiliation:	
Address of the affiliation:	
Webpage of the affiliation:	
ROR ID of the affiliation:	
1.5 What is the project duration? When does the project start and end?	The project is planned to run / has received funding for [Number of months]. The project will start / has started on _____ and will end on _____.
1.6 What DFG discipline does the study belong to?	The study belongs to the following disciplines: 204 Microbiology, Virology und Immunology 205 Medicine 206 Neurosciences
	Please specify further:

1.7 Who is funding the study?

The study / project is founded by:

Name of Funder:

Funding identifier:

2 Types of data – content

2.1 What data types are generated?

Administrative databases
 Biological samples
 Cognitive measurements
 Genealogical records
 Imaging data
 Interview
 Medical records
 Omics technology
 Physiological/Biochemical measurements
 Questionnaire
 Registries
 Other

Biosamples:
 Blood
 Buccal cells
 Cord blood
 DNA
 Faeces
 Hair
 Immortalized cell lines
 Isolated pathogen
 Nail
 Plasma
 RNA
 Saliva
 Serum
 Tissue (FFPE)
 Tissue (frozen)
 Urine
 Other biological samples

Imaging data:
 Computed tomography (CT)
 Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)
 Radiography (x-ray)
 Ultrasound
 Other imaging data
 Omics technology:
 Biomarkers
 Genomics
 Metabolomics
 Proteomics
 Transcriptomics
 Other omics technology

2.2 Are data reused?

Yes

No -> skip question 2.2.a + 2.2.b

2.2.a Which data are reused (secondary used)?

Administrative databases Biological samples Cognitive measurements Genealogical records Imaging data Interview Medical records Omics technology Physiological/Biochemical measurements Questionnaire Registries Other	Biosamples: Blood Buccal cells Cord blood DNA Faeces Hair Immortalized cell lines Isolated pathogen Nail Plasma RNA Saliva Serum Tissue (FFPE) Tissue (frozen) Urine Other biological samples	Imaging data: Computed tomography (CT) Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) Radiography (x-ray) Ultrasound Other imaging data Omics technology: Biomarkers Genomics Metabolomics Proteomics Transcriptomics Other omics technology
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2.2.b Are the re-used data (secondary used data) publicly available?

No	
Yes, some re-used data are publicly available here:	
Yes, all re-used data are publicly available here:	
DOI:	
URL:	
arXiv:	
EAN13:	
EISSN:	
Handle:	
ISBN:	
ISSN:	
ISTC:	
LISSN:	
LSID:	
PMID:	
PURL:	
URN:	
w3id:	

2.3 Which data are not digitally available?

Other:		
Administrative databases Biological samples Cognitive measurements Genealogical records Imaging data Interview Medical records Omics technology Physiological/Biochemical measurements Questionnaire Registries Other	Biosamples: Blood Buccal cells Cord blood DNA Faeces Hair Immortalized cell lines Isolated pathogen Nail Plasma RNA Saliva Serum Tissue (FFPE) Tissue (frozen) Urine Other biological samples	Imaging data: Computed tomography (CT) Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) Radiography (x-ray) Ultrasound Other imaging data Omics technology: Biomarkers Genomics Metabolomics Proteomics Transcriptomics Other omics technology

3 Data Formats

3.1 In which file formats and volumes are the data types created?

Hint: If these values have already been recorded elsewhere, it is sufficient to provide a corresponding reference and the storage location of the values

Text documents .pdf .docx .rtf .odt Data Volume:	Plain text .txt Data Volume:
Markup language .xml .html .css	Audio .bwf .mxf .mka

<p>Data Volume:</p>	<p>.flac .wav .mp3 .m4a</p> <p>Data Volume:</p>
<p>Programming languages</p> <p>Python Java MATLAB NetCDF</p> <p>Data Volume:</p>	<p>Video</p> <p>.mxf .mkv .mp4 .m4a .mpg .avi</p> <p>Data Volume:</p>
<p>Spreadsheets</p> <p>.ods .csv .xlsx .pdf</p> <p>Data Volume:</p>	<p>Computer Aided Design (CAD)</p> <p>.dxf .svg .dxf .dwg</p> <p>Data Volume:</p>
<p>Databases</p> <p>.sql .siard .csv</p> <p>Data Volume:</p>	<p>Geographical Information Systems (GIS)</p> <p>.gml .mif/.mid .json</p> <p>Data Volume:</p>

<p>Statistical data .dat/.sps .dat/.DO .csv/.html R .sav</p> <p>Data Volume:</p>	<p>Georeferenced images .tif/.tiff</p> <p>Data Volume:</p>
<p>Raster images .jpg/.jpeg .tif/.tiff .png .dcm</p> <p>Data Volume:</p>	<p>3D .obj .ply .x3d .dae .pdf</p> <p>Data Volume:</p>
<p>Vector images .svg .ai .eps .cdr</p> <p>Data Volume:</p>	<p>RDF .rdf .trig .ttl .nt</p> <p>Data Volume:</p>
<p>The collected digital data types are expected to take up a volume of [Number of] KB / MB</p>	

3.2 What is the expected data volume of all the digital data types to be collected (approximately)?

3.3 What is the expected data volume per year (approximately)?

The yearly rate of generated data is expected to be [Number of] KB / MB

3.4 Which instruments, software, tools are used to generate data?

The following software / tools are needed to generate the data ...

Scripts:

Software:

Documentation:

3.5 What software, processes or technologies are required to analyse the data?

The following software / tools are needed to analyse the data ...

Scripts:

Software:

Documentation:

3.6	What software or analysis scripts will be necessary in order to be able to reuse data?	The following software / tools are needed to reuse the data ...	
		Scripts:	
		Software:	
		Documentation:	
3.7	Where is the data saved during the research project?	local server	
		cloud service	
		if applicable, insert URL:	
3.8	Are there internal project guidelines for the uniform data organisation?	There are no project-internal guidelines for the uniform organisation of data.	
		There are project-internal guidelines for the uniform organisation of data:	
		Storage space	
		Folder structure	

3.9 Who is authorised to access which data during the research project?

File naming	
If applicable: insert LINK to guidelines	
Authorised person/group:	
Type of access:	
Type of accessible data:	
3.10 Who backs up the data and how often?	
IT	How often:
Researchers	How often:
Other	How often:

4 Interoperability/Metadata

4.1 Which metadata standards, ontologies, classifications etc. are used to describe the data?

The following metadata standards / ontologies / classification are used to describe the data:	
MeSH	
ICD-10	
ICD-11	
MedDRA	
SNOMED CT	
Other vocabulary:	
None	

4.2 Which data are not interoperable? For which data types/content are no (common) standards or project-specific (or rare) ontologies, metadata schemas, vocabularies etc. used?

Describe the type of data:

4.3 Will mappings be created for common metadata standards (for those data that do not use any standard)?

If applicable, name the standard:

4.4 Are metadata collected automatically (e.g. from devices)? Which ones?

Yes	
Instruments:	
Software:	
Variables:	
No	

5 [Persistent Identifiers \(PIDs\)](#)

5.1 Which PID system(s) is/are used?

	DOI URL arXiv EAN13 EISSN Handle ISBN ISSN ITC LISSN LSID PMID PURL URN w3id Other:
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5.2 Which data are given its own identifier?

Raw data:	
Cleaned data:	
Analysed data:	
Processed data:	
Published data:	

6 [Laws and ethics](#)

6.1 Which law is relevant for the project with regard to personal data protection issues?

6.2 Does the data set contain sensitive data (BDSG §3, para.9)?

No
Yes, information on: racial and ethnic origin political opinions religious or philosophical beliefs

		trade union membership health sex life
		other non-personal sensitive data:
6.3	Will the sensitive data anonymised be pseudonymised?	Personal data will be anonymized
		Personal data will be pseudonymised
		Undecided
6.4	Is the "informed consent" of the data subjects (=participants or legal guardian of participant) obtained? What research purposes does informed consent cover?	Research purposes covered by informed consent:
		Where are the informed consent documents stored:
6.5	Are data used that are protected by copyright?	Yes
		No

6.6 Is there a license or usage agreement for the re-used data specified in 2.2.a?

No

Yes, the following license / usage agreement applies:

6.7 Who is the ethics committee?

The Ethics Committee of:

6.8 Who decides if data access is granted in response to requests?

There is no data access committee.

There is a data access committee that decides whether access is granted for access requests. The committee consists of [Person / Department]:

7 [Reuse and publication of data](#)

7.1 Where do you plan to publish metadata and/or study documents?

Institutional repository:

Specialised repository:	
Generic repository:	
Data Journal:	
Other:	

7.2 Which study documents do you plan to publish?

Study metadata will be made publicly available on:	
Repository:	
Link:	
The following study documents/instruments will be made available on:	Repository, Link
Substudy/Data collection event	
Biobank	
Case report form	
Code book	
Data dictionary	

Data management plan	
Dataset	
Discussion guide	
Informed consent form	
Interview scheme and themes	
Manual of operations (SOPs)	
Observation guide	
Participant tasks	
Patient information sheet	
Questionnaire	
Registry	
Secondary data source	
Statistical analysis plan	
Study protocol	
Other data collection instrument	
Other study document	
Other	
7.3 Under which terms of use / which licence should the data be published?	Creative Commons 4.0
	Please specify:
	Individual data usage contracts

7.4 Are there embargo periods (for political/commercial/patent law reasons)? If yes, please provide details.

Yes:

No

7.5 Will individual patient data (IPD) be made available on request?

Yes

No

Undecided

7.5.a Where will individual patient data (IPD) be made available on request?

The IPD will be made available upon request here: [LINK]

7.5.b Which individual patient data (IPD) will be made available (on request)?

The following IPD will be made available:

8 Storage and long-term archiving

8.1 Where are the data (including metadata, documentation and any relevant code or software) stored or archived?

The data will be archived in a public repository	
Name of repository:	
URL:	
The data will be archived in a non-public repository (i.e., the data's existence is verifiable, but data is only accessible on request)	
Name of repository:	
URL:	
The data will be archived in a storage service, integrity and accessibility of the data are guaranteed	
Name of repository:	
URL:	
8.2 Which data will be archived for the long term?	Study metadata:
	Study documents:
	Instruments (templates):

IPDs:	
Software/Scripts:	

Basis: RDMO catalogue of questions (generic catalogue) of 19.11.2019

Lizenz

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